

A Study on the Role of Central Government towards Labour Welfare Measures

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Abstract

From the origination of labour welfare activities in 1837 till recent period notable changes have taken place giving a prime importance for the workers considering welfare measures to be an effective investment of every organization. The Central Government, State Government, trade unions and other organisations are playing a lead role in the effective planning and implementation of labour welfare measures for boosting the morale of the employees. In recent years, even the private sector organisations are also implementing such welfare measures. This paper deals with the welfare schemes provided by the central government. The author has highlighted the various theories, principles and benefits of welfare measures mentioning the intra mural and extra mural facilities. The paper concludes that even though schemes are provided by the government, the employers should also take a lead role investing these schemes in order to maintain a healthy and productive organization.

Keywords: Welfare Schemes, Central Government, benefits, intra mural and extra mural.

Introduction

The betterment of economic status of a nation depends on the rapid industrialisation which is the main national activity. Rapid industrialization has brought a tremendous change in securing large scale employment opportunities to the people. Labour plays a vital role in the industrial production of the country. In the previous era, industrialists and the employers were confined to the pay fair wages and salaries to the employees considering that it was the only welfare measure to satisfy employees. The present era, has totally changed the situation by introducing the concept Human Resources Management. The Indian Government enacted and is also in the process of enacting various rules and regulations for the betterment of labourers which would help to improve their socio economic status. Social welfare is broader in meaning covering the happiness, satisfaction, conservation and development of human resources which in turn would lead to the contribution for greater industrial efficiency which in turn results in the economic development of a nation.

Employee welfare measures enable workers to raise their standard of living and lead a more satisfactory life. These measures are framed to take care of the well - being of the employees, which are not usually monetary benefits, provided not only by the employees but also by government and non-governmental agencies and also includes trade unions. Any organization can be effective and efficient when there is a higher degree of cooperation between the labour and management. In short employee welfare stresses the adoption of facilities to promote physical, social, psychological and general well - being of the working people. In short, labour welfare measures is an important investment in any organization.

Concept of Welfare

According to the International Labour Organisation, “Workers welfare can be understood as meaning such as services, facilities and amenities which may be established in, or in vicinity of, an undertaking to enable the persons employed thereto perform their work in healthy congenial surrounding and provides all voluntary acts by employer aimed at improvement and betterment of workers social, moral and socio economic and intellectual conditions.

Review of Literature

Sanjay Upadyaya (2006) in the study “Awareness and Implementation of Labour welfare Measures-A case study at Garment Industry of Noida has found that nearly 84% of the workers engaged in the industry are unskilled/semiskilled workers. The earning levels of 2/3rd of the workers engaged Most of the workers engaged in the industry are unorganised and the contractual nature of employment reduces the chances of forming Trade Unions. Piece rated employees are not entitled to many of the benefits like payment of over time, casual leave, annual leave, earned leave etc because their names are not on the muster rolls. Most of the workers were not aware of various employee welfare provisions and 80% of the respondents covered under the study works for more than 9 hours per day which is more than the normally permitted limit. Women were not being paid over time rate. Only 10% of the units were providing food facility on a subsidised basis and only 5% of the units were providing transportation facilities to workers. 52% of the respondents belonging to the unskilled category were being paid wages which is less than the amount stipulated under the Minimum Wages act, 1948. So in short there has been a substantial violation of labour laws and great exploitation of illiterate workers by the owners of the industrial units.

Sreenivasa Rao and P V Ramana (2011) in the study “A study on employee welfare programmes at Lanco Industries Ltd at Srikalahasti, Andhra Pradesh has suggested that benefits like housing loans and PF benefits should be made available to all levels of employees in the organisation. Health camps and health checkups should be carried out every 3 months instead of 6 months. The author has also suggested that management should organise recreational and cultural programmes at the middle and lower management level and also implement flexible timing and shifts for the production and security departments.

Statement of the Problem

The progress of an economy depends on the development of Public Sector Undertakings. Like other nations, India’s development too reflects on the Public Sector Undertakings. Many effective welfare schemes under various acts passed and implemented by the Central Government helps to Public Sector Undertakings to function effectively and efficiently to achieve higher productivity and profitability. An attempt has been made in this research to understand the various welfare schemes provided by the government which takes a credit to improve the socio economic conditions of workers.

Need of the Study

Labour welfare measures should enable workers to live a more richer life, contribute more to the productivity of labour and efficiency of an organization, be an intelligent projection of the future needs of organization and essentially project the developmental outlook.

Scope of Labour Welfare

It includes all statutory and non – statutory measures provided by the government, employers, trade unions or voluntary organisations that bring together welfare activities and social securities which are the main components of labour welfare.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the theories of labour welfare
- To review the principles of labour welfare.
- To understand the role of central government and trade unions in providing various welfare measures provided to Public Sector Undertakings.
- To know the benefits of labour welfare measures.

Theories of Labour Welfare

- **The Police theory** of Labour welfare which is based on the fact that a minimum standard of welfare is necessary for labourers. The emphasis of the theory is based on the fear of punishment due to constant supervision and not on the spirit of welfare.
- **The Religious theory** states that man is related to religious sentiments and beliefs. It is neither religious nor continuous.
- **The Philanthropic Theory** depends largely on man's love or other.
- **The Trusteeship theory** depends on the initiative of the top management its value related to the moral conscience of the industrialist.
- **The Placating Theory** is based on the fact that labourers groups are becoming demanding and militant and are more conscious of their rights and privileges than even before.
- **Public Relations Theory** provides the basis for an atmosphere of goodwill between labour and management and also between management and the public.
- **The Functional theory** is used as a means to secure, preserve and develop the efficiency and productivity of labour.

Principles of Labour Welfare

- Management should be welfare oriented at every level.
- Welfare measures should not be supplemented to adequate wages of workers.
- Welfare of employees should be considered as a social obligation of all employers.
- Labour welfare aims workers to be responsible and more efficient.
- It should ensure for proper co - operation, co – operation, harmony, integration and active participation of unions in extending services and formulation and implementation of labour welfare measures.
- There should be periodical evaluation of welfare measures which would help for timely improvements and feedback.

Role of Central Government in Labour Welfare

The central government's Ministry of Labour provides various schemes focusing on the welfare and social security of the working people and the efforts for maintaining industrial peace. Various

laws have also been enacted and schemes established by the central/ state government providing for social security and welfare of specific categories of working people such as

The Workmen's Compensation Act, 1923

The provisions of this Act is administered exclusively by the state governments.

The Employees State Insurance Act, 1948

The cash benefits under the ESI Act is administered by the Central Government whereas the medical facility is administered by the State Governments and Union Territories.

The Employees Provident Funds and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1953

The EPF and MP Act is administered by the Government of India. The EPF Organisation is a statutory body of the Government of India under the Ministry of Labour and Employment to administer the Provident Fund Scheme, Pension Scheme and Insurance Scheme.

The Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972

The Act is administered by the central government in the establishments under its control and those establishments having branches more than in one state.

The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961

The provisions of maternity benefit are administered by the Central Government through the Chief Labour Commissioner and also by the state Government in various other organisations.

There are a planned initiatives in the welfare sector such as

- Training for skill development
- Services that provide assistance to job seekers
- The administration of labour regulations.

The central government has introduced Personal Accident Insurance and Social Security Scheme for those workers who are not covered under any Act or Insurance scheme. Another initiative by the Ministry of Agriculture is to provide insurance to the labourers in the unorganized sector working in the construction industry, agriculture and forestry. The Directorate General of Mines Safety (DGMS) and Directorate General of Factory Advice Service and Labour Institutes (DGFASLI) are responsible for regulating occupational safety and health in the country's mines, factories and ports.

Role of Trade Unions in Promoting Labour Welfare

Sec 2(h) of the Trade Unions Act 1926 defines a trade union as any organization, whether temporary or permanent, formed primarily for the purpose of regulating the relations between workers and employers, between workers and employers, between workers and workers, and the employers and employers or for imposing restrictive conditions on the conduct of any trade or business and includes any federation of two or more trade unions.

The functions they perform are:

- Representation
- Negotiation
- Voice in decisions affecting workers
- Member services
- Education and training
- Legal assistance
- Financial discounts
- Welfare benefits

Measures of Labour Welfare

Employer Labour Welfare Amentities	
Intra Mural	Extra Mural
Drinking Water	Social Insurance eg. Gratuity, Pension, Etc
Toilets	Benevolent Fund
Creche	Maternity Benefits
Washing Facilities	Health and Medical Facilities
Occupational Safety	Family Planning
Uniforms and Protective Clothing	Educational Facilities
Shift allowance	Recreation Facilities
Canteen	Leave Travel Allowance
	Worker's Co-operative
	Vocational Training
	Transport to and from place of work

Benefits of Welfare Activities

- Welfare activities helps to increase the co-operation and a sense of belonging with the management among workers and removes unrest and conflict which helps to establish harmony and peace.
- Sound welfare measures helps to improve the workers capacity and efficiency leading to higher productivity and reduced wastage and inefficiency in their part.
- Welfare measures are a motivational factor for the employees to stay back with the organization reducing labor turnover and absenteeism.
- A well – organized welfare scheme can develop a sense of loyalty and commitment of workers towards the organization.
- It helps in improving the health and morality by motivating them.
- A sense of responsibility, self - confidence and self – respect develops for the employees with proper working of welfare activities.
- It provides a higher satisfactory family life, higher standard of living and good status in the society.

Conclusion

Labour welfare has become the important integral part of every organization. The need for labour welfare has been realized in India because of the socio-economic conditions and problems faced by the labourers which hasnot been given concentration by the industrialists. The current concept of labour welfare is a comprehensive one concerning the development of total human personality embracing physical, mental, social psychological and spiritual aspects of the employees well - being. Many studies show that labour welfare schemes help workers to live a richer life as well as improve the productivity and efficiency of these workers which in turn leads to higher productivity of the organization and promote healthy industrial relations. It also enhances their active participation in their job and work with a sense of involvement and participation. The government is now playing a triple role of a legislator, administrator and promoter. Though the Government has enacted so many laws for the welfare of workers, India comparatively stands below the standard with other countries. Labour welfare schemes needs to be considered by Indian employers as a worthy investment since they provide the organization with a healthy, stable and productive labour force.

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